

Toxicity of Chemotherapy in Induction Phase of Childhood Acute Leukemia

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Abstract

Background: Leukemia is the most common childhood malignancy worldwide, and acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) comprises most pediatric leukemia. With risk-adapted intensive chemotherapy, the cure rate of pediatric ALL approaches nearly 80%. However, this intensive treatment may also bring about a number of significant morbidities during chemotherapy treatment. **Aims of study:** To detect toxicity-related morbidity & mortality during the induction phase of acute leukemia. **Methods:** A prospective study was done between 1/1/2015 to 31/12/2015; after exclusion of 17 patients, only data of 87 patients were analyzed (ALL 64 patients, AML 23 patients) below the age of 14 years with newly diagnosed acute leukemia whom were treated and followed thereafter. All medical records and laboratory data were collected; a chart review was performed. Follow up was made on daily bases to detect any complication according to the common toxicity criteria during the induction phase of chemotherapy. **Results:** The median age was 54 months for (ALL) (range 2 to 156 months) & 58 months (range 10 to 147 months) for AML, Male: Female ratio was (1:1.2). The duration of onset of symptom was 4 weeks for (ALL) & 3 weeks for AML. Initial leukocyte count of $\geq 50 \times 10^9/L$ was found in 20(31.2%) (ALL) patients & 2(8.6%) AML patients, Central Nervous System (CNS) disease was documented in 7(8%) patients. flowcytometry was done for 27 samples, it helped in changing the diagnosis in 8 cases. For (ALL) patients; 23(35.9%) were standard risk group & 41(64%) high risk; remission induction was reported in 63(98.4%) patients. one (ALL) patient died during induction without achieving remission. For AML patients 20(86.9%) patients got remission after (including 3 patients with APL) induction. One patients died during induction without BMA assessment. BM was not in remission after induction for two patients. The major presumptive causes of death were infection/sepsis. The main toxicity recorded during induction was the hematological events, 100% for both (ALL) & AML patients. GIT complication was reported in 25(39%) (ALL) patients & 10(43.4%) in AML patients. CNS events 18(28.1%) (ALL) patients, 2(8.6%) AML patients. Febrile neutropenia was reported in 48(75%) (ALL) patients & 15(65.2%) AML patients. **Conclusion:** Induction mortality was significantly reduced in patients with acute leukemia in the oncology unit/children welfare teaching hospital during 2013 compared with the previous 10-15 years.

Keywords: patients, leukemia, hematology, oncology.

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Introduction

Leukemia is the most common childhood malignancy worldwide, and acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) comprises most pediatric leukemia. With risk-adapted intensive chemotherapy, the cure rate of pediatric ALL approaches nearly 80%. However, this intensive treatment may also bring about a number of significant morbidities during chemotherapy treatment [1,2].

During the treatment for acute leukemia (AL) a patient may experience a wide variety of complications that mainly have three possible origins, namely the disease itself (leukemic infiltration), peripheral blood cell depression (because of hemorrhagic or infectious processes) and toxicity induced by chemotherapy.

The toxicity of chemotherapy is a common cause of morbidity and mortality in cancer patients, as well as a frequent source of sequelae at mid-long term. These adverse effects are often the consequence of

direct toxicity in healthy tissue, as a result of the low specificity displayed by these drugs. Furthermore, and regardless of their specificity, these compounds may also exacerbate complications derived from the tumor growth, as it is the case of pancytopenia or the Tumor Lysis Syndrome [3]. Chemotherapy toxicity becomes more frequent as the treatment is intensified, thus challenging the clinician with both diagnostic and therapeutic problems. In order to identify subjects at higher risk of toxicity, a complete clinical-analytical evaluation must be performed in all patients before the administration of each chemotherapy cycle. Furthermore, clinicians should be familiar with the different metabolic pathways of each administered drug, and doses should be adjusted accordingly if necessary, especially in cases with decreased renal or liver function. However, even with these precautions, chemotherapy-induced toxicity is still an important clinical concern in AL [4]. Indeed, at

the present time the cornerstone of therapy for AL is still formed by a reduced number of drugs with a highly toxic profile.

The present challenge would therefore be to reduce the frequency and seriousness of adverse effects while maintaining efficacy and avoiding overtreatment of patients. The design of new drugs such as the so-called molecular target drugs, the further development of existing therapeutic groups, or the knowledge of genetic determinants of toxicity may help achieve these goals [5].

Patients and Methods

Patients

Between January 1st to December 31st 2015; 104 patients below the age of 14 years with newly diagnosed acute leukemia whom were treated and followed at the oncology unit of Children Welfare Teaching Hospital (CWTH) were studied.

All medical records and laboratory data were collected; A chart review was performed to determine their age, gender, residence, duration of onset before referral, any steroid treatment before diagnosis, signs and symptoms of disease, date of diagnosis, results of initial investigations, place of treatment, details of induction phase of treatment and outcome of induction.

From 104 acute leukemia; 17 patients were excluded from the analysis:

- 1- Two patients with acute leukemia who died before doing BMA.
- 2- Two patients with ALL-L3 were treated with different protocol.
- 3- Three patients treated in other centers then referred to our unit; 2 ALL & 1 AML.
- 4- Five patients sent for treatment in other centers just after the diagnosis; 3 ALL & 2 AML
- 5- Two patients discharged on family responsibility; 1 ALL & 1 AML
- 6- One AML down patient kept untreated for follow up only.
- 7- Two AML patients died within 24 hours from admission (one of them was Down syndrome)

Only data of 87 patients were analyzed in this study:

- 1- ALL; 64 patients.
- 2- AML; 23 patients.

Diagnosis

The diagnosis of acute leukemia was established by bone marrow aspirate (when it contained at least 25% lymphoblasts). Morphological classification of the blast cells according to FAB system was carried, Immunophenotyping and karyotyping facilities were available for some patients.

Most of the patients underwent lumbar puncture for CSF analysis; the definition of central nervous system (CNS) involvement was based on the presence of any number of white blood cells (WBCs) per microliter of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) with leukemia cells on a cytocentrifuged smear, or the presence of cranial nerve palsies. For practical purposes; every blast in the cytospin was considered to be CNS disease if the sample was not traumatic. In addition in some patients regarded as CNS disease depending on radiological images.

All patients had been evaluated by Chest X-Ray for the presence of mediastinal mass.

Risk Classifications

Patient's risk groups were assessed depending on age, initial WBCc, BM morphology at time of diagnosis. Treatment protocols were used based on type and subtype of leukemia, the response to pre-phase steroid for patients with ALL.

Therapy

1. Regimen Modified from MRC UKALL 2003; for 52 patients, 50 ALL & 2 AUL, those patients were stratified either having Standard Risk (SR) if they were 1-9 years old with a presenting leukocyte count of less than $50 \times 10^9/L$, otherwise they were regarded as High Risk (HR). (6)

2. NHL/BFM-95 Protocol; for 12 patients with presumptive T-Cell ALL based on morphology and clinical assessment (borderline age with high WBCc and the presence of mediastinal mass).(7)

3. APL based protocol; for 3 patients with AML M3,(8) and

4. MRC AML 15 protocols; for 20 patients having other than M3 subtype.(9-10)

5. Two patients with AUL were treated initially with MRC UKALL 2003 protocol and were assessed for response at the end of induction.

Response Criteria

Response to treatment was assessed during induction therapy for ALL and AML.

- **Complete remission (CR)** was defined as the absence of Leukemic blasts in peripheral blood & CSF and less than 5% blast on bone marrow (BM) aspirate smear, together with hematopoietic regeneration and no evidence of extramedullary (localized) disease.

- **Partial responder** is labeled when the BM contain 5-25% blast cells

- **Non responder** is labeled when the BM contains >25% blast cells.

Induction failure was defined as failure to achieve remission within 6 weeks in ALL and after two induction courses in AML.

Supportive care was given when indicated to patients with fever, febrile neutropenia, anemia and bleeding and also to those with presumed or proved tumor lysis syndrome. Antibiotics, platelets transfusion, plasma transfusion, blood transfusion, allopurinol and excessive hydration were given to patients when indicated accordingly. The available analgesics were prescribed also whenever indicated.

Follow Up

Beside the routine follow up of the patient daily by the medical team, a specific follow up was made by two fellows in the unit after the morning round and sometimes at night for the critical patients.

The follow up includes questionnaire from the mother or the patient, general examination, blood pressure measurement was done at presentation and supposed to be done every 1-2 weeks, neurological assessment as indicated, weight measurement every 2 weeks, detection of early signs of infection.

PT & PTT was done to all patient at time of presentation then it was measured either weekly or just in 3rd week then stopped after a period of observation.

Complication of chemotherapy were followed on a daily basis and graded according to Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) version 4.0. (11)

An Adverse Event (AE) is any unfavorable and unintended sign (including an abnormal laboratory finding), symptom, or disease temporally associated with the use of a medical treatment or procedure that may or may not be considered related to the medical treatment or procedure.

Grades

Grade refers to the severity of the AE. The CTCAE displays Grades 1 through 5 with unique clinical descriptions of severity for each AE based on this general guideline:

Grade 1 Mild; asymptomatic or mild symptoms; clinical or diagnostic observations only; intervention not indicated.

Grade 2 Moderate; minimal, local or noninvasive intervention indicated; limiting age-appropriate instrumental ADL*.

Grade 3 Severe or medically significant but not immediately life-threatening; hospitalization or prolongation of hospitalization indicated; disabling; limiting self care ADL**.

Grade 4 Life-threatening consequences; urgent intervention indicated.

Grade 5 Death related to AE.

For the purpose of study, only grade 3 & 4 were considered to be mentioned in the results tables of toxicity.

Results

Patient Characteristics

The analysis identified 104 patients that met the diagnosis of acute leukemia who were below 14 years, the analysis was limited to 87 patients after excluding 17 patients who didn't met the purpose of the study.

Most of the patients in the study were from Baghdad 37 (42.5%) patients, followed by Diyala 15 (17.2%), Wasit 11 (12.6%), Thiqr 6 (6.8%) and Karbala 4 (4.5%) as shown in table (1).

Table 1: Referral Pattern of 87 children (Age 0 to 14 years) treated at the CWTH

Governorate	No. (%)	ALL	AML
Total	87 (100)	64	23
Baghdad	37 (42.5)	27	10
Diyala	15 (17.2)	13	2
Wasit	11 (12.6)	8	3
Thiqr	6 (6.8)	2	4
Karbala	4 (4.5)	4	0
Najaf	3 (3.4)	2	1
Qadisiya	3 (3.4)	2	1
Muthanna	2(2.2)	2	0
Babil	2 (2.2)	1	1
Anbar	2 (2.2)	1	1
Meesan	1 (1.1)	1	0
Salah Aldeen	1 (1.1)	1	0

The detailed demographic data of the 87 patients are presented in table (2). The median age was 54 months (range 2 to 156 months) for ALL and 58 months (range 10 to 147 months) for AML, 39 (44.8%) males (30 ALL and 9 AML) & 48 (55.1%) females (34 ALL and 14 AML) forming Male: Female ratio of (1:1.2). The median duration of onset of symptoms was 4 weeks for ALL and 3 weeks for AML (range 2 days to 8 months for ALL and 2 days to 7 months for AML). There was 1 case ALL and 4 cases AML with Down syndrome.

Table 2: Demographic Data of 87 children (Age 0 to 14 years) treated at the CWTH

	ALL		AML		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No	%
Total	64	73.5	23	26.4	87	100
Age						
1-12 months	3	4.6	2	8.6	5	5.7
13-120 months	55	85.9	17	73.9	72	82.7
121-168 months	6	9.3	4	17.3	10	11.4
Median / months	58		54			
Gender						
Male	30	46.8	9	39.1	39	44.8
Female	34	53.1	14	60.8	48	55.1
Duration of onset						
< 6 weeks	40	62.5	17	73.9	57	65.5
6 weeks – 6 months	23	35.9	5	21.7	28	32.1
> 6 months	1	1.5	1	4.3	2	2.2
Median/ weeks	4		3			
Down syndrome	1	1.5	4	17.3	5	5.7

The clinical data are shown in table (3). Fever was reported in 75 (86.2%), pallor in 78 (89.6%), bleeding tendency in 20 (22.9%), and

lymphadenopathy was recorded in 40 (45.9%) patients. Hepatomegaly and splenomegaly (≥ 5 cm below costal margin) were recorded in 41 (47.1%) and 35 (40.2%) of patients, respectively.

Table 3: Demographic Data of 87 children (Age 0 to 14 years) treated at the CWTH

	ALL		AML		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No	%
Total	64	73.5	23	26.4	87	100
Fever	54	84.3	21	91.3	75	86.2
Pallor	57	89	21	91.3	78	89.6
Bleeding tendency	13	20.3	7	30.4	20	22.9
Lymphadenopathy	32	50	8	34.7	40	45.9
Hepatomegaly \geq 5cm BCM	37	57.8	4	17.3	41	47.1
Splenomegaly \geq 5cm BCM*	29	45.3	6	26	35	40.2

Initial Laboratory and Radiological features

Table 4 and 5 shows the profile of laboratory and radiological findings: The hemoglobin level ranged between (3.9 – 12.7) g/dl for ALL with a median of (7.2) g/dl and (3.6 – 11.7) g/dl for AML with a median of (6.6) g/dl. Initial leukocyte count ranged from ($1-748 \times 10^9/L$) with a median of ($19.7 \times 10^9/L$) for ALL, while initial leukocyte count for AML ranged from ($0.5-219 \times 10^9/L$) with a median of ($39.0 \times 10^9/L$). Thirty one (35.6%) patients had an initial leukocyte count of $\geq 50 \times 10^9/L$ (20 ALL and 9 AML). The median platelets count was ($29 \times 10^9/L$) (range 3.8-281 $\times 10^9/L$) for ALL and was ($27 \times 10^9/L$) (range 5.5-193 $\times 10^9/L$) for AML. Thrombocytopenia was observed in 60 ALL patients (93.7%) and 22 AML patients (95.8%).

Table 4: Initial Laboratory & Radiological results of 87 children (Age 0 to 14 years) treated at the CWTH:

Data	ALL		AML		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Overall	64	73.5	23	26.4	87	100
Hemoglobin (g/dl)						
<6g/dl	16	25	6	26	22	25.2
6-10g/dl	37	57.8	16	69.5	53	60.9
>10g/dl	11	17.1	1	4.3	12	13.7
WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)						
<10	26	40.6	6	26	32	36.7
10-49.99	16	25	8	34.7	24	27.5
≥ 50	22	34.3	9	39.1	31	35.6
Platelets ($\times 10^9/L$)						
<20	17	26.5	8	34.7	25	28.7
20-99.99	39	60.9	11	47.8	50	57.4
≥ 100	8	12.5	4	17.3	12	13.7
CSF cytopsin						
CSF cytopsin positive	2	3.1	2	8.6	4	4.5
CSF cytopsin negative	62	96.8	18	78.2	80	91.9
Missing	0	0	3	13	3	3.4
Mediastinal mass (CXR)						
Present	16	25	2	8.6	18	20.6
Absent	48	75	21	91.3	69	79.3

Table 5: Morphological & flowcytometry classification of 87 children treated at the CWTH

ALL			AML		
	Total	%(valid)		Total	%(valid)
	64	100		23	100
FAB/ ALL-L1	2	3.1(4.8)	FAB/ AML-M1	1	4.3(7.1)
FAB/ ALL-L2	39	60.9(95.2)	FAB/ AML-M2	5	21.7(35.7)
FAB/ Unclassified ALL	14	21.8	FAB/ AML-M3	3	13(21.4)
FAB/ Possible T cell	3	4.6	FAB/ AML-M4	0	0
FAB/ AUL	1	1.5	FAB/ AML-M5	2	8.6(14.2)
Flowcytometry ALL	5	7.8	FAB/ AML-M6	1	4.3(7.1)
			FAB/ AML-M7	2	8.6(14.2)
			FAB/ Unclassified AML	4	17.3
			Flowcytometry AML	5	21.7

Of 87 patients; CSF analysis in 80 (91.9%) samples were normal, 4 (4.5%) samples were positive (2 ALL and 2 AML), another 3 patients (1 ALL and 2 AML) had clinical and/ or radiological signs of CNS disease while their CSF cytospin was negative forming a total of 7 (8%) patients with CNS disease at presentation.

Mediastinal mass was detected in 16 (25%) ALL patients and 2 (8.6%) AML patients.

The default diagnosis was based on morphological assessment of the bone marrow based using FAB classification. Table 5

Flowcytometry was done for 27 samples according to the availability of the test; it helped in changing the diagnosis in 8 cases: table 5

- Acute leukemia; 4 patients, the diagnosis was changed into ALL in 3 & AML in 1.
- Acute undifferentiated leukemia; 5 patients, the diagnosis was changed into ALL in 2 & AML in 3.
- Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma; the diagnosis was changed into AML.

Treatment Outcome

The treatment outcome is shown in table.6;

Table 6: Treatment Results of 87 children (Age 0 to 14 years) treated at the CWTH

Treatment Phase	ALL			AML
	Total	Standard risk	High risk	Total
Total No.	64(100%)	23(35.9%)	41(64%)	23 (100)
Non responders	0	0	0	2
Died within 30 days	1**	0	1	1
Complete remissions	63 (98.4%)	23(100%)	40 (97.5%)	20(86.9%)

Note: ** Marrow not in remission at day 8

For ALL patients; 23 (35.9%) patients were standard risk and 41 (64%) high risk. All 64 patients received induction chemotherapy; 63 (98.4%) achieved complete remission (CR) by the end of induction.

One patient died during induction; he was a high risk T-cell patient, died at day 29 of induction without achieving remission.

From 23 AML patients, 20 patients got remission after induction, 2 patients were non-responders, and one patient died during induction without BMA assessment.

Adverse Events during Induction

Adverse events during induction were categorized per systems.

Adverse event in ALL:

Hematology system was affected in 64 patients with ALL; neutropenia was observed in 62 patients followed by thrombocytopenia in 52 patients

and anemia in 50 patients. Febrile neutropenia was seen in 48 patients that mandated antibiotic use.

Hemorrhage was detected in 2 patients; one of them got profuse oral bleeding with malena, the other got fresh bleeding per rectum, treated with blood and platelets transfusion.

Deep venous thrombosis occurred in one patient who got left calf pain, limitation of movement and tender, hot lower limb, she was kept on low molecular weight heparin till the end of induction.

Although not serious event; alopecia occurred in 50 patients.

GIT system was affected in 25 patients; stomatitis occurred in 13 patients followed by nausea and vomiting in 10 patients.

Tumor lysis syndrome occurred in one boy; age 9 years with WBCc of 748,000/cmm, he developed oliguria, turbid color urine, significant elevation in urea, creatinine and hypocalcemia after rapid steroid response, he was treated with vigorous hydration and ca gluconate according to clinical assessment, he improved within 1st week.

Hyperglycemia defined as Random blood sugar \geq 200 mg/dl occurred in 1 (1.6%) patient that required insulin till the end of induction, another 5 patients got hyperglycemia grade I & II which didn't need any intervention apart from monitoring.

The blood pressure of all patients were measured at time of presentation; only 35 patients rechecked 1-2 times during induction, one (2.8%) of them got hypertension that required antihypertensive during and after induction.

Other serious events occurred in ALL patients were dyspnea in 5, weigh loss in 2, hepatic failure and enterocolitis (1 patient for each).

Adverse event in AML:

All patients got hematological complications, all of them got significant anemia and thrombocytopenia, although 21 patients got neutropenia but 15 patients got febrile neutropenia.

Other serious events were:

- Depressed level of consciousness in one patient
- Stomatitis in 3
- Lung infection in 3
- Weight loss in 2

Liver, renal and skin toxicities were not noticed during AML induction.

Death in patient with ALL was due presumptive sepsis with or without pulmonary fungal infection.

Median duration of stay in ALL was 31 days (range 23-54 days) while the median duration of stay in AML was 17 (range 9-40 days)

Discussion and Conclusions

At the CWTH, protocols for childhood ALL were mainly based on the UKALL schemes; the unavailability of chemotherapeutic agents, delayed administration of drugs and the limitation of intensive supportive measures affected the results. In order to improve childhood ALL outcome, in the framework of the Italy-Iraq Telemedicine project [12-16],

it was focused on modulating treatment intensity according to a simple strategy for risk stratification. The steroid pre-phase was introduced as a further risk indicator and in order to improve the clinical and metabolic status before the start of chemotherapy. In addition, during the weekly telemedicine consultations a continuous assessment of patient's outcome in real time with multidisciplinary discussions of problematic patients and detailed analysis of all deaths was carried out. With these measures, the early treatment related mortality (TRM) in children with ALL remarkably decreased from 24 to 10% during 2007-2009 [17-19]. All the efforts to further reduce the induction mortality failed to achieve this mission during 2010-2012.

Using modified MRC 12 in the period 2000-mid 2008; the induction mortality was 40%, this figure was reduced to 22% when MRC15 were used (omission of VP16) in the period mid2008-2011 [20-22].

All the efforts to further reduce the induction mortality wasn't successful till 2013 when the number of newly diagnosed patients with cancer were reduced from over 350 before 2013 to 265 during 3013.

The current induction mortality for ALL was 1.6% and for AML was 4.3%. Improvement in the survival might be explained by the following:

- Better access to supportive drugs (antibiotics, antifungals).
- The use of single donor platelets rather than multiple donor type.
- Use of duanorubicin rather than doxorubicin.
- Decrease the number of newly admitted patients during 2013 offered better place for patient isolation.
- Strict treatment of patients regarding the place, Treatment of patients in single rooms rather

Hematological complication was expected to occur during treatment of induction of both ALL & AML as the main pathology of leukemia is the bone marrow which affects all the blood elements. Incidence of hyperglycemia occurred in 1 (1.6%) in ALL patients lower previous studies with incidence of 4–15% of pediatric ALL patients [23], the high incidence of hyperglycemia in other studies might be secondary to the overall increase in childhood obesity in these studies.

Improvement in the diagnostic studies for coagulation profiles and Doppler studies made it possible to diagnose cases with thrombosis.

Although tumor lysis syndrome occurred mostly after treatment with lymphoma, it occurs in patients with leukemia as well [24].

Hypertension was documented in 1/35(2.8%) patient during the study period, lower than figures in other studies of 15.3% [25].

Other complications occurred in patients with ALL and AML like mucositis pulmonary infection, skin infection and UTI indicate the level of risk to the patient with acute leukemia receiving chemotherapy as the long period of stay in the hospital, poor hygiene of the families in addition to the poor infrastructure of the hospital and absent of infection control policy might have a major impact on the clinical progress of the patients and ultimately the survival.

Two patients died during induction; one ALL and one AML, both of them died with presumptive sepsis and fungal infection, those patients were treated in the oncology ward as there is no intensive care unit for the critically ill patients, the measures were modest as there was no central venous line, absent of dependable blood culture results and other biochemical assessment.

Induction mortality during 2013 for both ALL & AML was the lowest results since 15 years in this ward.

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